

Performance analysis of a tactile-based architecture for collaborative robots

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Abstract—Tactile sensors represent an intuitive and efficient interface for physical Human-Robot Interaction (pHRI). To ensure the safety of the human during industrial collaborative tasks we mounted four cylindrical-shaped handles, covered with the CySkin technology, over the gripper of an industrial manipulator, through which the operator can express his intention to physically interact. Tactile data are fed into a neural network that recognizes human touch during grasp, thus providing an enabling command for the control system. In this paper we present a performance analysis of the perceptual architecture based on distributed tactile sensors for Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC). The inference time comparison performed in this activity considers two computing architectures: a desktop workstation with a high-performance GPU and an embedded solution based on the NVIDIA Jetson Nano board. The inference time performance analysis also considers three different neural network optimization engines: Keras, TensorRT floating-point 16 and TensorRT floating-point 32. The results show that numerically optimized models allow to perform inference within the timing constraints even on the embedded architecture. An inference robustness analysis is also performed to verify if voluntary touch recognition fails when the user wears work gloves, showing negligible differences from bare-hand grasps.

Index Terms—Tactile Sensing, physical Human-Robot Interaction, Deep Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Safety, productivity and synergy are the key elements of a successful Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC). In traditional manufacturing systems industrial robots lack the necessary sensory equipment to achieve an effective collaboration with humans and are commonly confined into a restricted workspace for safety reasons. To overcome this limitation it is essential to enhance robots perceptual capabilities by using external sensing devices. Thus robots become aware of their surroundings, unexpected collisions may be avoided and benefits in terms of speed and accuracy may be achieved.

The general context of this activity concerns physical Human-Robot Interaction (pHRI), i.e. the human and the robot not only share the same working environment, but physically interact to accomplish a common goal. This working configuration is very effective from an industrial point of view because it leverages the robot accuracy and strength to fulfill monotonous and dangerous tasks and human dexterity, fast adaptability and fine manipulation skills to solve complex problems and handle new situations.

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Fig. 1. CoLLaboratE technology demonstration: assembly of a car windshield

Tactile sensors are the technology that is generally used in pHRI applications because it allows humans to intuitively express their intention to physically interact with a robot and, at the same time, ensure a safe collaboration. To prove it, we built a technology demonstration within the CoLLaboratE H2020 project [1] for the assembly of a car windshield, requiring the collaboration between a human operator and a heavy-weight industrial robot. In particular, the robot is intended to compensate and absorb the weight of the car windshield, while the human is instructed to inspect and assemble over the windshield different types of sensors and components. To adjust the windshield to a comfortable position and orientation, the operator must simply grasp one or more of the sensorized handles placed all over the robot gripper, as described in detail in [2]. The sensorized handles are covered with the CySkin technology [3], a flexible artificial skin composed by distributed tactile sensors, which measure the pressure distribution resulting from the physical interaction and thus generate a tactile image [4]. Whenever a human hand tactile image is classified by HandsNet, the Convolutional Neural Network outlined in [5], the robot admittance controller is enabled. Otherwise, the motion of the robot is disabled.

In this paper we present a performance analysis of the perceptual architecture based on distributed tactile sensors for Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC). The inference time comparison considers: 1) two computing architectures, a desktop workstation with an RTX 3070 GPU and an embedded solution based on the NVIDIA Jetson Nano board; 2) three different neural network optimization engines: Keras [6], TensorRT floating-point 16 and TensorRT floating-point 32 [7].

An inference robustness analysis is also performed to verify if touch recognition fails when the user wears work gloves,

Fig. 2. Cylindrical handle covered with Cyskin technology and tactile image generated by a bare-hand grasp

showing negligible differences from bare-hand grasps.

II. INFERENCE TIME ANALYSIS

The core of this paper concerns the inference time performance evaluation of the hand tactile images, performed over two different computational architectures:

- An on-board solution which relies on a Jetson Nano board. This solution is self-contained, but has some constraints in terms of space, power and resources.
- An external desktop workstation with an RTX 3070 GPU by NVIDIA, which has no restrictions in terms of processing architecture, but requires more space.

The comparative analysis also considers three different instances of the HandsNet CNN: the plain Keras model, directly obtained from the building framework, and two optimized models obtained through the compilation with TensorRT (TRT), an optimization toolchain for GPU architectures. The main timing constraint for this application is $T = 0.05s$, given by the acquisition frequency $f = 20Hz$ of CySkin.

Table I show that the Keras model has a poor time performance compared to TRT models on both devices: only on the desktop workstation the time constraints are met on average, even though peaks reaching $0.0808s$ are detected. TensorRT models, instead, provide acceptable results in terms of inference time on both computational architectures.

TABLE I
RESULTS OF THE INFERENCE TIME ANALYSIS IN SECONDS (S).

	RTX 3070			Jetson Nano		
	mean	max	std	mean	max	std
Keras	0.0216	0.0808	0.0038	0.1991	0.6786	0.0438
TensorRT fp16	0.0016	0.0024	$9.8 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.0083	0.0224	0.0017
TensorRT fp32	0.0016	0.0022	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.0065	0.0225	$8.01 \cdot 10^{-4}$

III. INFERENCE ROBUSTNESS ANALYSIS

Voluntary interaction is determined from a tactile image by the classification of a human hand shape whenever a sensorized handle is grasped. In this activity we also ran an inference robustness analysis to verify if the use of protective gloves interferes with the classification of human hand shapes. Indeed, strict safety standards [8] dictate the use of protective

clothing, such as work gloves, to increase the safety of humans in assembly departments. However, the neural network was originally trained with bare hand grasps.

We acquired data from a user grasping one fixed handle and holding the grasp for two minutes while randomly rotating the wrist to emulate the small motions that occur during robot motion. We analyzed the probability value of the hand class in terms of mean, minimum value and standard deviation and we noticed that wearing a work glove has a small impact on the prediction value, as depicted in Table II. In particular the presence of the glove slightly increases fluctuations as can be seen by observing the standard deviation and the minimum value, but in terms of classifications these values are negligible even by choosing a tight threshold of 0.9 to enable the controller.

TABLE II
COMPARISON BETWEEN HAND CLASS PROBABILITY IN BARE HAND GRASP AND WORK GLOVE GRASP. THE RESULTS REPRESENT PROBABILITY VALUES, DIMENSIONLESS AND LIMITED BETWEEN 0 AND 1.

	mean	min	std
bare hand	1.00	0.99	$5.14 \cdot 10^{-6}$
work glove	0.99	0.95	0.0019

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we presented an overview of the activity carried out for the CoLLaborate H2020 project and, in particular, the performance analysis conducted for the tactile sensing architecture used for a physical Human-Robot interaction application. We evaluated the impact of the computational architecture and deep learning model optimization in terms of inference time, showing that an embedded board provides a prediction within the sampling period of $0.05s$. The performances obtained by both fp16 and fp32 models on the Jetson Nano board are comparable to those observed on the RTX 3070. We also tested the robustness of our hand classification model, comparing the results obtained from bare-hand grasps with grasps performed wearing work gloves. The results obtained show that work gloves do not affect voluntary interaction detection.

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